

Supplementary Information

Faster model-based estimation of ancestry proportions

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Supplementary methods

Quasi-Newton acceleration scheme

We here describe the quasi-Newton scheme [1] used to accelerate the expectation-maximization (EM) algorithm of `fastmixture`. For simplicity and speed, we only utilize one secant condition ($q = 1$) in the scheme for both the mini-batch and the full EM updates such that the update rule is a combination of two standard EM steps. We define $\mathbf{Q}^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{P}^{(1)}$ as the updated matrices after one standard EM step, using Equation 2 and Equation 3, respectively, and $\mathbf{Q}^{(2)}$ and $\mathbf{P}^{(2)}$ after two successive standard EM steps. The accelerated update rules are then described as follows and we refer to the original paper on the quasi-Newton scheme for more details:

Algorithm S1 quasi-Newton acceleration

Given: $\mathbf{G}, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{P}$

- 1: $\mathbf{Q}^{(1)}, \mathbf{P}^{(1)} \leftarrow \text{em}(\mathbf{G}, \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{P})$ ▷ First EM step
- 2: $\mathbf{Q}^{(2)}, \mathbf{P}^{(2)} \leftarrow \text{em}(\mathbf{G}, \mathbf{Q}^{(1)}, \mathbf{P}^{(1)})$ ▷ Second EM step
- 3: $\mathbf{D}_Q^{(1)}, \mathbf{D}_P^{(1)} \leftarrow \mathbf{Q}^{(1)} - \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{P}^{(1)} - \mathbf{P}$ ▷ First difference matrices
- 4: $\mathbf{D}_Q^{(2)}, \mathbf{D}_P^{(2)} \leftarrow \mathbf{Q}^{(2)} - \mathbf{Q}^{(1)}, \mathbf{P}^{(2)} - \mathbf{P}^{(1)}$ ▷ Second difference matrices
- 5: $\mathbf{D}_Q^{(3)}, \mathbf{D}_P^{(3)} \leftarrow \mathbf{D}_Q^{(2)} - \mathbf{D}_Q^{(1)}, \mathbf{D}_P^{(2)} - \mathbf{D}_P^{(1)}$ ▷ Third difference matrices
- 6: $c_Q, c_P \leftarrow \frac{\langle \mathbf{D}_Q^{(1)}, \mathbf{D}_Q^{(1)} \rangle_F}{\langle \mathbf{D}_Q^{(3)}, \mathbf{D}_Q^{(1)} \rangle_F}, \frac{\langle \mathbf{D}_P^{(1)}, \mathbf{D}_P^{(1)} \rangle_F}{\langle \mathbf{D}_P^{(3)}, \mathbf{D}_P^{(1)} \rangle_F}$ ▷ Step multipliers using Frobenius inner products
- 7: $\mathbf{Q} \leftarrow (1 - c_Q)\mathbf{Q}^{(1)} + c_Q\mathbf{Q}^{(2)}$ ▷ quasi-Newton update for \mathbf{Q}
- 8: $\mathbf{P} \leftarrow (1 - c_P)\mathbf{P}^{(1)} + c_P\mathbf{P}^{(2)}$ ▷ quasi-Newton update for \mathbf{P}

Return: \mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{P}

Assessment measures

We here describe the different assessment measures used in the study. The log-likelihood estimate is already defined in Equation 1. \mathbf{Q} refers to the estimated ancestry proportions and \mathbf{Q}^* refers to the simulated ground truth ancestry proportions.

Root mean square error (RMSE)

$$\text{RMSE}(\mathbf{Q}^*, \mathbf{Q}) = \frac{1}{NK} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K (q_{ik}^* - q_{ik})^2. \quad (\text{S1})$$

Jensen-Shannon divergence (JSD)

$$\text{JSD}(\mathbf{Q}^*, \mathbf{Q}) = \frac{1}{2} (\text{KLD}(\mathbf{Q}^*, \mathbf{X}) + \text{KLD}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{X})), \quad (\text{S2})$$

where $\mathbf{X} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{Q}^* + \mathbf{Q})$ and $\text{KLD}(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the Kullback–Leibler divergence:

$$\text{KLD}(\mathbf{Q}, \mathbf{X}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^K \left(q_{ik} \log \frac{q_{ik}}{x_{ik}} \right). \quad (\text{S3})$$

Simulated data overview

All demographic models and scripts for reproducing the simulation scenarios are available on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12683371>).

Common msprime options

- Segment length: 250 Mb
- Mutation rate: 2.36×10^{-8}
- Recombination rate: 1.28×10^{-8}

Scenario A

- $N = 1,000$ (250 individuals from each of the 4 simulated populations)
- $M = 689,563$
- 3 ancestral populations (POP1, POP2, POP3)
- 1 admixed population (POP1: $\frac{1}{3}$, POP2: $\frac{1}{3}$, POP3: $\frac{1}{3}$)

Scenario B

- $N = 1,000$ (200 individuals from each of the 5 simulated populations)
- $M = 687,107$
- 4 ancestral populations (POP1, POP2, POP3, POP4)
- 1 admixed population (POP1: $\frac{1}{4}$, POP2: $\frac{1}{4}$, POP3: $\frac{1}{4}$, POP4: $\frac{1}{4}$)

Scenario C

- $N = 1,600$ (200 individuals from each of the 8 simulated populations)
- $M = 685,592$
- 5 ancestral populations (POP1, POP2, POP3, POP4, POP5)
- 1 admixed population (POP1: $\frac{1}{5}$, POP2: $\frac{1}{5}$, POP3: $\frac{1}{5}$, POP4: $\frac{1}{5}$, POP5: $\frac{1}{5}$)
- 1 admixed population (POP1: $\frac{1}{3}$, POP2: $\frac{1}{3}$, POP3: $\frac{1}{3}$)
- 1 admixed population (POP4: $\frac{1}{2}$, POP5: $\frac{1}{2}$)

Scenario D

- $N = 1,000$ (250 individuals from each of the 4 simulated populations)
- $M = 500,114$
- 3 ancestral populations (AFR, EUR, EAS)
- 1 admixed population (AFR: $\frac{1}{6}$, EUR: $\frac{1}{3}$, EAS: $\frac{1}{2}$)

Supplementary figures and tables

Figure S1: **A.** Demographic model of *Scenario A* with 250 individuals sampled from each of the four populations. **B.** Admixture plots of the ancestry proportions in the simulated individuals for $K = 3$ with the ground truth at the top followed by the different software using their run with the highest log-likelihood.

Figure S2: **A.** Demographic model of *Scenario B* with 200 individuals sampled from each of the five populations. **B.** Admixture plots of the ancestry proportions in the simulated individuals for $K = 4$ with the ground truth at the top followed by the different software using their run with the highest log-likelihood.

Figure S3: **A.** Demographic model of *Scenario D* (American admixture [2]) with 250 individuals sampled from each of the four populations. **B.** Admixture plots of the ancestry proportions in the simulated individuals for $K = 3$ with the ground truth at the top followed by the different software using their run with the highest log-likelihood.

Figure S4: Admixture plots of the ancestry proportions in the simulated individuals for $K = 5$ of *Scenario C* by *fastmixture* with different batch sizes for $B = \{8, 16, 32, 64, 128\}$ using their run with the highest log-likelihood.

Figure S5: Admixture plots of the ancestry proportions in the simulated individuals for $K = 5$ of *Scenario C* by *fastmixture* with different types of initialization using their run with the highest log-likelihood.

Figure S6: Admixture plots of the ancestry proportions in the simulated individuals for $K = 2$ of *Scenario C* by the different software using their run with the highest log-likelihood.

Figure S7: Admixture plots of the ancestry proportions in the simulated individuals for $K = 3$ of *Scenario C* by the different software using their run with the highest log-likelihood.

Figure S8: Admixture plots of the ancestry proportions in the simulated individuals for $K = 4$ of *Scenario C* by the different software using their run with the highest log-likelihood.

Figure S9: Admixture plots of the estimated ancestry proportions for $K = 5$ in the downsampled version of the 1000 Genomes Project dataset (1KGP Down) by the different software using their run with the highest log-likelihood. AFR: African, EUR: European, EAS: East Asian, AMR: American, and SAS: South Asian ancestry.

Dataset	fastmixture	Neural ADMIXTURE	ADMIXTURE	SCOPE
A	2.70 (0.23)	3.97 (0.06)	77.85 (17.97)	1.69 (0.08)
B	3.09 (0.23)	3.98 (0.05)	105.34 (18.33)	1.96 (0.10)
C	7.11 (0.63)	6.09 (0.06)	202.22 (34.27)	2.31 (0.49)
D	1.32 (0.19)	2.97 (0.07)	36.72 (2.37)	0.24 (0.01)
1KGP Down	6.62 (0.42)	10.44 (0.21)	275.24 (12.77)	1.97 (0.25)
1KGP	82.74 (8.13)	113.54 (3.59)	2439.92*	18.69 (2.27)

Table S1: Computational runtimes (in minutes) for the different simulated and empirical datasets for the evaluated methods. The mean across five different runs is reported with the corresponding standard deviation in parenthesis. All analyses have been performed on a cluster with an Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6152 CPU using 64 threads. *ADMIXTURE has only been evaluated on a single run for 1KGP due to excessive runtime.

Scenario	fastmixture	Neural ADMIXTURE	ADMIXTURE	SCOPE
A	0.0093 (4.2e-5)	0.0211 (0.0070)	0.0094 (1.3e-7)	0.0252 (3.0e-5)
B	0.0079 (4.5e-5)	0.2075 (0.0044)	0.0079 (1.5e-7)	0.0331 (4.2e-5)
C	0.0082 (4.6e-5)	0.1957 (0.0072)	0.0083 (1.4e-7)	0.0398 (2.9e-5)
D	0.0008 (6.7e-7)	0.0187 (0.0129)	0.0008 (4.5e-8)	0.0058 (1.1e-6)

Table S2: Jensen-Shannon divergence (JSD) measures for the estimated ancestry proportions in the three different simulated datasets for the evaluated methods against the ground truth. The mean across five different runs is reported with the corresponding standard deviation in parenthesis.

Dataset	fastmixture	Neural ADMIXTURE	ADMIXTURE	SCOPE
A	-637729493.6 (0.5)	-640197951.4 (39763.0)	-637729492.4 (0.5)	-637845454.1 (10.0)
B	-629360598.6 (0.1)	-633930570.4 (37694.0)	-629360598.5 (1.6)	-629538330.5 (38.1)
C	-1006294346.2 (0.6)	-1013880607.9 (52010.8)	-1006294347.6 (4.1)	-1006604915.2 (244.3)
D	-429286152.5 (0.2)	-433792567.4 (627402.9)	-429286155.6 (4.1)	-429536651.1 (25.0)
1KGP Down	-1509950457.3 (0.8)	-1531090301.0 (228164.6)	-1509950464.3 (7.5)	-1510431876.5 (254.2)
1KGP	-15097015793.7 (4.9)	-15342582278.2 (3449977.8)	-15097016096.0*	-15101701104.4 (2807.9)

Table S3: Log-likelihood measures in the different simulated and empirical datasets for the evaluated methods. "1KGP" refers to data from the 1000 Genomes Project, where "1KGP (down)" is the downsampled variant. The mean across five different runs is reported with the corresponding standard deviation in parenthesis. *ADMIXTURE has only been evaluated on a single run for 1KGP due to excessive runtime.

Population	fastmixture	Neural	ADMIXTURE	ADMIXTURE	SCOPE
POP1	0.0188	0.0329		0.0189	0.0700
POP2	0.0220	0.0039		0.0221	0.0704
POP3	0.0253	0.0399		0.0254	0.0752
POP4	0.0314	0.0048		0.0316	0.0904
POP5	0.0310	0.6324		0.0312	0.0836
ADMIX1	0.0295	0.3408		0.0294	0.0294
ADMIX2	0.0220	0.3404		0.0220	0.0367
ADMIX3	0.0209	0.3138		0.0209	0.0421

Table S4: Root mean square error (RMSE) measures for the estimated ancestry proportions in the eight populations of Scenario C for the evaluated methods against the ground truth.

Population	fastmixture	Neural	ADMIXTURE	ADMIXTURE	SCOPE
POP1	0.0086	0.0195		0.0087	0.0478
POP2	0.0105	0.0007		0.0106	0.0482
POP3	0.0124	0.0200		0.0124	0.0514
POP4	0.0140	0.0003		0.0142	0.0612
POP5	0.0138	0.6930		0.0139	0.0564
ADMIX1	0.0029	0.2731		0.0029	0.0028
ADMIX2	0.0022	0.2607		0.0022	0.0220
ADMIX3	0.0015	0.2118		0.0015	0.0283

Table S5: Jensen-Shannon divergence (JSD) measures for the estimated ancestry proportions in the eight populations of Scenario C for the evaluated methods against the ground truth.

Mini-batches	Runtime (m)	Log-likelihood	RMSE	JSD
$B = 8$	7.86 (1.18)	-1006294348.7 (1.4)	0.0258 (4.5e-5)	0.0084 (2.9e-5)
$B = 16$	7.11 (0.68)	-1006294345.3 (1.0)	0.0256 (5.1e-5)	0.0083 (3.0e-5)
$B = 32$	7.11 (0.63)	-1006294346.2 (0.2)	0.0255 (8.7e-6)	0.0082 (4.9e-6)
$B = 64$	7.53 (0.80)	-1006294353.9 (1.4)	0.0254 (2.2e-5)	0.0082 (2.2e-5)
$B = 128$	9.82 (2.32)	-1006294360.1 (1.5)	0.0254 (7.9e-6)	0.0081 (6.7e-6)

Table S6: Assessment measures in the simulated dataset of Scenario C using different initial numbers of batches, B , in fastmixture. The mean across five different runs is reported with the corresponding standard deviation in parenthesis.

Initialization	Runtime (m)	Log-likelihood	RMSE	JSD
Random	14.12 (1.03)	-1006294348.5 (0.6)	0.0255 (3.2e-5)	0.0082 (2.0e-5)
SVD-based	7.11 (0.63)	-1006294346.2 (0.2)	0.0255 (8.7e-6)	0.0082 (4.9e-6)

Table S7: Assessment measures in the simulated dataset of Scenario C using `fastmixture` for two different parameter initialization approaches. The mean across five different runs is reported with the corresponding standard deviation in parenthesis.

	<code>fastmixture</code>	Neural ADMIXTURE	ADMIXTURE	SCOPE
$K = 2$	-1015395537.1 (0.1)	-1016467332.7 (5479.3)	-1015395536.6 (0.0)	-1015464044.1 (0.0)
$K = 3$	-1011420272.3 (0.7)	-1014984382.1 (274833.2)	-1011420270.5 (0.2)	-1011552464.8 (0.1)
$K = 4$	-1008338857.0 (0.4)	-1014255193.2 (127570.6)	-1008546129.6* (463478.4)	-1008524838.1 (4.7)
$K = 5$	-1006294346.2 (0.2)	-1013880607.9 (52010.8)	-1006294347.6 (4.1)	-1006604915.2 (244.3)

Table S8: Log-likelihood measures in the simulated dataset of Scenario C using `fastmixture` for different values of K , the number of ancestral populations assumed in the ancestry estimation. The mean across five different runs is reported with the corresponding standard deviation in parenthesis. *ADMIXTURE had 4/5 runs finding the optimal solution.

Supplementary References

- [1] Hua Zhou, David Alexander, and Kenneth Lange. A quasi-newton acceleration for high-dimensional optimization algorithms. *Statistics and computing*, 21:261–273, 2011.
- [2] Sharon R Browning, Brian L Browning, Martha L Daviglus, Ramon A Durazo-Arvizu, Neil Schneiderman, Robert C Kaplan, and Cathy C Laurie. Ancestry-specific recent effective population size in the americas. *PLoS genetics*, 14(5):e1007385, 2018.